

The Application of a Coaching Program in Teachers: The Perception, the Understanding and the Capacity to Deal with the Emotions

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to verify the influence of a coaching training program on the perception, comprehension, and capacity to deal with emotions in Portuguese teachers. The sample consisted of thirteen teachers with more than ten years of teaching experience, with a mean age of 48.73 years (SD = 6.26). Wilcoxon's test ($p \leq 0.05$) revealed statistically significant results in the ability to deal with emotions and with increases in the values of the emotional variables at the end of the program. We conclude that the coaching program will have had an influence on a dynamic of knowledge of the emotions in the participating individuals, being a key element in the different emotional experiences.

Keywords: Coaching, Emotion, Teacher, Program, Teaching

Introduction

Defining the competencies of teachers for 21st century education may be complex but possible given the generic competencies of human performance with an emphasis on the emotions of their social and educational role (Bécart, 2016). In an organizational context such as education the group work, peer, bi-directional and students take on capital importance. In this sense, coaching can be a relevant tool that can reinforce and improve the effectiveness and functioning of working groups (Marques, Dimas & Lourenço, 2014, Dias, Palmer & Nardi, 2017). The influence that exists between individuals at the inter-group level, as well as extra-group and all-encompassing will define success and understanding of performance.

Emotions are part of our day-to-day life and have repercussions not only on an individual basis but also on the groups and contexts in which each individual inserts (Marques et al., 2014, Santos, 2017). However, some authors (Duffel & Lawton-Smith, 2015) point out that emotions may become inconvenient and need to be regulated, or even ignored, being irrelevant but it will be impossible to do any work among the actors without regard for emotions because it shows us the importance of emotions in any and all contexts of learning. Because the emotions always associated with learning with meaning, reinforce and improve the anchors of knowledge and competence. Understanding and accepting the power of emotions can be the starting point for any change.

Hakman's Normative Group Effectiveness Model (1983) points to the importance of coaching that includes support for learning and improvements in skills and knowledge of individuals. The importance of Emotional Intelligence has a high positive relation with coaching (Dave, Farin & Farin, 2017), being a preponderant factor in the evolution in the individual (Goleman, 1995). Emotional Intelligence is the ability to sense, understand, control and guide mood states, provides the ability and ability to regulate the forces and impulses of negative emotions, as it speeds up and improves decision making, increasing emotional control. An increasing number of studies referred to Emotional Intelligence competencies as important for teaching and social / emotional competencies (Bolev & Lesham, 2016).

Individuals become autonomous through the teaching / learning strategies they develop, creativity and their competencies (Bécart, 2016; Santos, 2017) making coaching as a promoter and reinforcement of emotional intelligence and emotional, behavioral and social competencies .

Some factors become of paramount importance as the feedback and the motivation of the individual, are aspects that lead us to improve and overcome difficulties like going to the next phases. However, the communication between the subjects involved can have a dramatic influence on the relationship between the coach and the subject (Duffel & Lawton-Smith, 2015), not only for the semantic field but also for the sense of language. Communication can influence the individual conception of the moment; the actors should speak the same language and see the world in the same perspective. The context and channels of communication as a means of communication will always be factors to take into account so that the coaching process can flow.

The participation of teachers in emotional regulation programs reveals significant results in competence, regulation, and expression of emotions (Ulloa, Evans & Jones, 2016),

Hypothesis

There is a significant relationship between coaching knowledge and emotions.

- The practice of coaching benefits the knowledge and ability to deal with emotions

The objective of the study was to verify the influence of a coaching training program on emotional intelligence in teachers of a faculty of a grouping of schools in the interior of Portugal.

Methodology

Sample

The sample consists of thirteen female teachers from different levels of education, from pre-school to secondary education, and with more than ten years of teaching practice, with a mean of 48.73 years (SD = 6.26).

Instrument

The instrument used to evaluate the dimensions "Expressions of emotions," "Perception of emotions" and "Ability to deal with emotions."

Procedures

The training program took place over two months, with the application of the questionnaire in two moments, initially with the first time (pre-test) and secondly at the end of the coaching program (post-test).

Statics Procedures

The results were expressed as means and their standard deviation, sample normality was tested and homogeneity according to test.

To define the differences between the two moments the Wilcoxon's Test ($p \leq 0.05$) was applied in the sample.

Results

We observed that the three variables (Expression of emotions, the perception of emotions and the ability to deal with emotions) had an increase in the values collected in the second moment (post-test). The results were statistically significant in the ability to deal with emotions ($p = ,027$).

Table 1 - Means and differences of the Wilcoxon test in the pre-test and post-test sample

	1° moment	2°moment	$p \leq ,05$
Expressions of emotions	4,00	4,11	,507
Perception of emotions	3,67	3,75	,594
Ability to deal with emotions	3,69	3,97	,027

N=13

There is substantial evidence, according to our data, that the way our study was defined and elaborated, demonstrated that a brief intervention focused on the individuals' experiences, knowledge, and emotional reflection process improves outcomes (Fig. 1), going against other studies (Dunsmore, Booker, Ollendick & Greene, 2016; Ulloa, Evans & Jones, 2016).

Figure 1 - Evolution of the values of Emotion variables of the pre-test and the post-test

Emotional regulation is at the basis of success in work and life in general, and satisfaction in any relation (Novotná, Blahová & Satanková, 2018), because emotional states affect behavior but are not always a cause / effect of it. We think that according to our data, possibly the teachers who participated in our study have become more aware of their psychophysical states, being in a better position to carefully balance the emotions in any condition and change the strategies to self-regulate and have a better performance.

Coaching enhances performance as it facilitates personal, professional, and social development such as improving commitment and motivation (Hollywood, Blaess, Santin & Bloom, 2016, Rose, Gilbert & McGuire-Snieckus, 2015). However, the appreciation of possibilities and their context represent an important determinant of decision making (Suri et al., 2017), which determines the choice and emotional regulation of the moment.

Discussion

The purpose of the study was to prove the influence of a coaching program on the understanding and perception of emotions, as well as on the ability to deal with emotions.

The results showed an increase in the three variables under study, "Expression of emotions," "Perception of emotions" and "Ability to deal with emotions" having a significant impact on the latter. Through the influence of the exercise of emotional formation and reflection practices, they place the importance of fostering the acquisition of emotional skills by teachers in order to satisfy and fulfill the emotional needs of children (Ulloa, Evans & Jones, 2016). as in other studies (Dolev & Lesham, 2016), our participants believe that participation in the program has improved their emotional and behavioral competencies, having a positive impact on their practice, as it has helped them to understand their students and their relationships with them better. Coaching is a universal strategy for emotionally and behaviorally supporting the educational and community context and promoting resilience in skills, the key elements reflecting a biopsychosocial model (Gus, Rose & Gilbert, 2015). We verified that in this group of work the practice of coaching benefited the knowledge and capacity to deal with the emotions. And there may be a significant relationship between coaching knowledge and emotions.

Conclusion

Every human being has a very own perception of the world that surrounds him, as he has a model and an ideal and very own image of himself. Coaching corresponds to the leader's actions aimed at helping individuals to walk their own path of self-development. It is a philosophy of leadership that is based on the idea that the development and acquisition of skills are continuous processes and responsibility, and are not only limited in time. It is a supportive process that fosters awareness; it is the development of the potential and capacities that exist in each individual. Understanding yourself and adapting it to the outside world becomes a challenge. Coaching is tools that will help the individual strengthen his or her daily personal development journey.

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